

Phenylazo derivatives of some unsaturated β -diketones and their metal complexes

K. Krishnankutty^{a*}, P. Sayudevi^b and Muhammed Basheer Ummathur^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Calicut-673 635, Kerala, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, NSS College, Manjeri-676 122, Kerala, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Unity Women's College, Manjeri-676 122, Kerala, India

E-mail : mbummathur@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Phenylazo derivatives of three β -diketones in which the diketo function attached directly to olefinic linkages (dicinnamoyl methane, acetyl cinnamoyl methane and benzoyl cinnamoyl methane) have been synthesized and characterised. Analytical, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data indicate that the compounds exist in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded keto-hydrazone form. In the [ML₂] complexes [M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}] the compounds function as monobasic bidentate in which one of the hydrazone nitrogen and keto oxygen are involved in bonding with the metal ion.

Keywords : Unsaturated β -diketones, phenyl hydrazones, metal complexes.

The coupling of aryl diazonium salts with 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds yield intramolecularly hydrogen bonded 2-arylaazo-1,3-dicarbonyls¹⁻³. Having wide application as yellow dyes and pigments^{4,5} these compounds are extensively used as intermediates in the preparation of a large number of biologically important heterocyclic compounds, and as precursors of potential antidiabetic drugs⁶. Arylazo derivatives of β -diketones are known to exist both in the azo and hydrazone forms. The relative percentage of the two forms is dependent on the nature of the aryl group and also on the type of the diketones. Thus phenylazo derivatives of 1,3-diketones exist entirely in the keto-hydrazone form while heteroarylaazo derivatives such as pyridylazo, thiazolylazo etc. exist predominantly in the azo-enol form⁷. Most of the reported studies are based on 1,3-diketones in which the diketo function directly linked to alkyl or aryl groups^{8,9}. No report appeared on arylazo derivatives of 1,3-diketones in which the diketo group linked to alkenyl function. Such unsaturated 1,3-diketones have gained considerable importance¹⁰ in recent years mainly because of the fact that these structural types constitute the major biologically active compounds present in several traditional Indian medicinal plants. The best-known example is the curcuminoids, (1,7-diaryl-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-diones), the active chemical constituent

of the herbaceous Indian medicinal plant turmeric (*Curcuma longa*, Linn, *Zingiberaceae* family). Curcuminoids, their synthetic analogues and their metal complexes are known to exhibit anticancer, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities¹¹. In this paper we report the synthesis and characterization of phenylazo derivatives of three synthetic analogues of the natural curcuminoids namely 1,7-diphenyl-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-dione (dicinnamoylmethane); 6-phenyl-5-hexene-2,4-dione (acetylcinnamoylmethane) and 1,5-diphenyl-4-pentene-1,3-dione (benzoylcinnamoylmethane). Metal complexes of these azo derivatives were also studied.

Results and discussion

The elemental analytical data of the phenylazo derivatives of the three unsaturated diketones (Table 1) indicate that diazo-coupling reaction has occurred in the 1 : 1 ratio. All the compounds are crystalline in nature and are soluble in common organic solvents. They formed stable complexes with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions. The analytical data (Table 2) together with non-electrolytic nature in DMF (specific conductance < 10 Ω^{-1} cm⁻¹; 10⁻³ M solution) suggest [ML₂] stoichiometry of the complexes. The Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} chelates are diamagnetic

Table 1. Analytical, ^1H NMR and mass spectral data of Hpad, Hpah and Hpap

Compd./ Empirical formula	m.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			^1H NMR (δ , ppm)				Mass spectral data (m/z)
			Found (Calcd.)			NH	Alkenyl	Aryl	Alkyl	
Hpad $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	160	70	78.64 (78.95)	5.24 (5.26)	7.28 (7.37)	16.52	8.22 (2H) 7.98 (2H)	6.80–7.80	–	380, 303, 277, 249, 226, 174, 146, 131, 118, 103, 92, 77
Hpah $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	142	72	73.84 (73.97)	5.50 (5.48)	9.57 (9.59)	16.46	7.90 (1H) 7.58 (1H)	6.80–7.50	2.58 (3H)	292, 249, 223, 215, 189, 161, 135, 131, 103, 92, 77
Hpap $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	134	74	77.86 (77.97)	5.11 (5.08)	7.88 (7.91)	16.32	7.98 (1H) 7.97 (1H)	6.50–7.58	–	354, 277, 251, 249, 223, 197, 131, 103, 92, 77

Table 2. Physical and analytical data of the metal complexes of Hpad, Hpah and Hpap

Complex/ Empirical formula	Yield (%)	m.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
			Found (Calcd.)			
			C	H	N	M
[Cu(pad) $_2$] $\text{C}_{50}\text{H}_{38}\text{CuN}_4\text{O}_4$	70	296	73.06 (73.03)	4.52 (4.63)	6.78 (6.82)	7.80 (7.73)
[Cu(pah) $_2$] $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{30}\text{CuN}_4\text{O}_4$	65	284	65.98 (66.92)	4.62 (4.65)	8.64 (8.67)	9.74 (9.84)
[Cu(pap) $_2$] $\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{34}\text{CuN}_4\text{O}_4$	60	274	71.86 (71.73)	4.42 (4.42)	7.34 (7.28)	8.20 (8.26)
[Ni(pad) $_2$] $\text{C}_{50}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_4\text{NiO}_4$	65	256	73.36 (73.47)	4.62 (4.65)	6.81 (6.86)	7.24 (7.19)
[Ni(pah) $_2$] $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_4\text{NiO}_4$	70	242	67.28 (67.43)	4.63 (4.68)	8.65 (8.74)	9.10 (9.16)
[Ni(pap) $_2$] $\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_4\text{NiO}_4$	75	270	72.10 (72.18)	4.41 (4.45)	7.24 (7.32)	7.65 (7.68)
[Zn(pad) $_2$] $\text{C}_{50}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Zn}$	74	198	72.70 (72.87)	4.51 (4.62)	6.70 (6.80)	7.85 (7.94)
[Zn(pah) $_2$] $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Zn}$	72	186	66.54 (66.73)	4.62 (4.63)	8.72 (8.65)	9.98 (10.10)
[Zn(pap) $_2$] $\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Zn}$	70	202	71.68 (71.56)	4.31 (4.41)	7.20 (7.26)	8.52 (8.48)

while Cu^{II} complexes showed normal paramagnetic moment. The observed electronic, IR, ^1H NMR and mass spectra are in conformity with structure 1 of phenylazo derivatives and structure 2 of their complexes.

Infrared spectra : The IR spectrum of Hpad in the region $1600\text{--}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is characterized by the presence of three strong bands at 1709 , 1651 and 1603 cm^{-1} assignable respectively to the stretching of free cinnamoyl carbonyl, intramolecularly hydrogen bonded cinnamoyl carbonyl and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching vibrations^{12,13} of

$\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$

Compd.	R	R ₁
Hpad	$-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	$-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$
Hpah	$-\text{CH}_3$	$-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$
Hpap	$-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	$-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

structure **1**. In the spectra of the complexes of Hpad, the band at 1709 cm^{-1} of the free ligand remained almost unaffected indicating that this carbonyl is not involved in complexation. However, in the spectra of all the complexes, the band due to the hydrogen bonded cinnamoyl carbonyl at 1651 cm^{-1} disappeared and instead a few strong band appeared at $\sim 1560\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to the stretching of metal bonded carbonyl group.

The IR spectrum of Hpah in the $1600\text{--}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region displayed strong peaks at 1705 , 1628 and 1610 cm^{-1} assignable respectively to the stretching of the cinnamoyl carbonyl, conjugated and intramolecularly hydrogen bonded acetyl carbonyl and $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ ^{14,15} in addition to several medium intensity bands in the range $1580\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to various $\text{C}=\text{C}$ vibrations. In the spectra of metal complexes, the free ligand band at 1628 cm^{-1} is absent and instead a new band appeared at $\sim 1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the involvement of metal ion in bonding with the acetyl carbonyl oxygen. The cinnamoyl carbonyl band (1705 cm^{-1}) is only marginally shifted in the spectra of complexes suggesting its non-involvement in complexation.

The IR spectrum of Hpap in the region $1600\text{--}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ consists of two strong bands at 1652 and 1668 cm^{-1} and a medium intensity band at 1612 cm^{-1} assignable respectively to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ of benzoyl carbonyl, intramolecularly hydrogen bonded cinnamoyl function¹⁶ and $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ of structure **1**. In the IR spectra of the metal complexes of Hpap the band of the free ligand at 1652 cm^{-1} showed only marginal shift. However the band at 1668 cm^{-1} due to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded cinnamoyl carbonyl disappeared and a new band appeared at $\sim 1560\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to metal bonded cinnamoyl carbonyl as in structure **2**.

The IR spectra of the three ligands are characterised by the presence of a broad band in the range $2500\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which clearly indicate the existence of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding as in structure **1**. However this broad band disappeared in the spectra of all the complexes and several medium intensity bands due to various $\nu\text{C}\text{--}\text{H}$ vibrations appeared in the region. This strongly supports the replacement of the chelated proton of the ligands by metal ion as in structure **2**. A prominent band present in the spectra of all the ligands at ~ 1540

cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{N}\text{--}\text{H}$ vibration disappeared in the spectra of all the complexes. This indicates that the metal ion replaced the hydrazone NH proton. That the hydrazone nitrogen and the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded carbonyl group are involved in complexation is clearly evident from the appearance of two additional bands at ~ 425 and $\sim 540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable of $\nu\text{M}\text{--}\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{M}\text{--}\text{N}$ vibrations¹⁷ in the spectra of complexes. Thus the IR spectra of the phenylazo derivatives of the unsaturated diketones strongly support the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded hydrazone-keto form as in structure **1**. Spectra of the complexes are in agreement with the formulation of $\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{OM}$ chelate ring as in structure **2**. Important bands that appeared in the spectra are given in Table 3.

¹H NMR spectra : The ¹H NMR spectra of the phenylazo derivatives of the unsaturated 1,3-diketones are characterized by the presence of a low field one proton signal at $\sim 16.5\text{ ppm}$ due to $\text{N}\text{--}\text{H}\cdots\text{O}=\text{C}$ group^{3,18}. The alkenyl group(s) and aryl groups show signals at positions as expected. The integrated intensities of all the signals agree well with the structure **1** of the compounds (Table 1). In the ¹H NMR spectra of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, the low field signal due to the chelated hydrogen disappeared indicating the replacement of the hydrazone proton by metal ion during complexation⁸. Integrated intensities of all other protons agree well with the structure **2**.

Mass spectra : The formulation of the compounds as in structure **1** is clearly supported from the presence of intense molecular ion peak in the mass spectra. Since peaks due to the elimination of N_2 from the molecular ion^{19,20}, a characteristic feature of the azo tautomer, has not been observed in the mass spectra indicate that the compounds exist in the hydrazone form. The formation of other important peaks are due to the elimination of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}$, C_6H_5 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}_2\text{H}_2$, etc. from the molecular ion or subsequent fragments (Table 1). The FAB mass spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes showed molecular ion peaks of appreciable intensity corresponding to $[\text{CuL}_2]$ stoichiometry. Peaks correspond to $[\text{CuL}]^+$, L^+ and fragments of L^+ are also present in the spectra. The spectra of all the chelates contain a number of fragments containing copper in the 3 : 1 natural abundance of ⁶³Cu and ⁶⁵Cu isotopes (Table 4).

Table 3. Characteristic IR stretching bands (cm^{-1}) of Hpad, Hpah, Hpap and their metal complexes

Compd.	Free (C=O)	Chelated (C=O)	(C=N)	(C=C) phenyl/alkenyl	(C-N)	(M-N)	(M-O)
Hpad	1709s	1651s	1603s	1598m, 1592m 1588m, 1580m	1280s	-	-
[Cu(pad) ₂]	1707s	1558s	1605s	1595m 1590m 1585m, 1582m	1268s	528m	422m
[Ni(pad) ₂]	1708s	1560s	1608s	1592m, 1588m 1585m, 1580m	1266s	525m	418m
[Zn(pad) ₂]	1707s	1559s	1606s	1596m, 1588m 1585m, 1580m	1266s	526m	420m
Hpah	1705s	1628s	1610s	1600m, 1595m 1588m, 1585m	1275s	-	-
[Cu(pah) ₂]	1710s	1552s	1612s	1602m, 1598m 1593m, 1586m	1258s	518m	428m
[Ni(pah) ₂]	1708s	1558s	1614s	1600m, 1596m 1592m, 1588m	1282s	530m	420m
[Zn(pah) ₂]	1708s	1554s	1612s	1600m, 1594m 1591m, 1588m	1282s	530m	420m
Hpap	1652s	1668s	1612m	1600m, 1596m 1595m, 1588m	1282s	-	-
[Cu(pap) ₂]	1652s	1562s	1605s	1598m, 1592m 1588m, 1585m	1272s	526m	418m
[Ni(pap) ₂]	1655s	1568s	1602s	1595m, 1590m 1586m, 1580m	1268s	522m	422m
[Zn(pap) ₂]	1654s	1564s	1603s	1597m, 1592m 1588m, 1581m	1270s	524m	419m

Electronic spectra : The UV spectra of the phenylazo derivatives of the unsaturated 1,3-diketones show two broad bands with maxima at ~ 360 and ~ 250 nm due to the various $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. In complexes these absorption maxima shifted appreciably to low wave numbers. The Cu^{II} complexes showed a broad visible

band, λ_{max} at $\sim 15000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This, together with the measured μ_{eff} values (1.75–1.80 B.M.) suggests the square-planar geometry. The observed diamagnetism and broad medium-intensity band at $\sim 17600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the Ni^{II} chelates suggest their square-planar geometry. In conformity, the spectra of the chelates in pyridine solution (10^{-3} M) showed three bands corresponding to configurational change to octahedral due to the association of pyridine²¹.

Table 4. Mass spectral data of Cu^{II} complexes of Hpad, Hpah and Hpap

Complex	Mass spectral data (m/z)
$\text{Cu}(\text{pad})_2$	823, 821, 692, 690, 561, 599, 720, 718, 617, 615, 514, 512, 444, 411, 409, 380, 303, 226, 174, 146, 131, 103, 92, 77
$\text{Cu}(\text{pah})_2$	647, 645, 516, 514, 544, 542, 441, 439, 413, 411, 385, 383, 356, 354, 292, 249, 189, 161, 135, 131, 103, 92, 77
$\text{Cu}(\text{pap})_2$	771, 769, 666, 664, 561, 559, 418, 416, 563, 561, 458, 456, 355, 353, 354, 277, 251, 197, 131, 103, 92, 77

Experimental

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen percentages were determined by micro analyses (Heraeus Elemental analyzer) at CDRI, Lucknow and metal contents of complexes by AAS (Perkin-Elmer 2380). The electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded on a 1601 Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The IR spectra were recorded using KBr discs on a 8101 Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer. The ^1H NMR spectra were recorded

in CDCl_3 or $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ on a Varian 300 NMR spectrometer. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol/SX-102 mass spectrometer (FAB using Argon and *meta*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix). Molar conductance of the complexes was determined in DMF at 28 ± 1 °C using solution of about 10^{-3} M concentration. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on a Guoy type magnetic balance.

Synthesis of phenylazo derivative of unsaturated 1,3-diketones, Hpad, Hpah and Hpap : The unsaturated 1,3-diketones, 1,7-diphenyl-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-dione; 6-phenyl-5-hexene-2,4-dione and 1,5-diphenyl-4-pentene-1,3-dione were synthesized as reported²². The phenylazo derivatives were synthesised by the coupling of benzene diazonium salt with the unsaturated 1,3-diketones. Benzene diazonium salt (0.01 mol) was prepared as reported²³. After destroying the excess nitrous acid with urea, it was added drop by drop to a solution of the unsaturated 1,3-diketone (0.01 mol in 20 mL methanol) kept below 0 °C with constant stirring. The pH of the solution was maintained around 6, using sodium acetate. The precipitated compound was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from methanol to get chromatographically pure (tlc) material.

Synthesis of metal complexes : The Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were prepared by the following general method. To a refluxing ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.02 mol, 20 mL) concentrated aqueous solution of the metal acetate (0.01 mol, 15 mL) was added, refluxed for ~2 h and the volume was reduced, cooled to room temperature and the precipitated complex was filtered, washed with excess water, then with methanol and dried in vacuum.

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